

DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE SYSTEM OF MODERN MODELS OF INTERACTION BETWEEN TAXPAYERS AND TAX AUTHORITIES

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Annotation. The article is devoted to a close analysis of digitalization in the life of the state and its citizens in the field of taxation. The article shows that digitalization affects relationships in all spheres of life, from the educational process to taxation. The author focuses on the fact that the state should first of all apply the principles of fairness and effective taxation in digitalization, so that the taxpayer can receive the necessary consultations and convenience of digital services, services and tax payments according to fair criteria, and the state can effectively monitor for tax receipts. However, the actions of artificial intelligence and the consequences of its use do not have a clear legal regulation. The article analyzes the errors of information programs, technical failures in their operation in terms of their impact on violations of the legitimate rights and interests of taxpayers and the state.

Keywords: tax administration, principles, taxation, property, digitalization, social justice, principles of property taxation, tax justice, efficiency, tax policy, mechanism.

Introduction. Taxes are an important link in financial relations in society and as a form of financial relations arise simultaneously with the emergence of the state. Being an integral part of the company's finances, tax payments have a significant impact on the financial condition of the company. The tax impact is so great that it can play a decisive role in shaping the strategy and tactics of economic development.

As the President of Uzbekistan Mirziyoyev Sh.M. noted, "The main goal of tax reform is to ensure economic stability in this and subsequent years. To do this, it is necessary to support producers and progressively increase budget revenues. Our only way is to increase the number of manufacturers and entrepreneurs, to realize the business potential of people." An important guide to action in implementing these priorities is the adoption of the Concept of Improving the Tax Policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which provides for fundamental reform of the tax system, including reducing taxes and mandatory payments, as well as the abolition of ineffective tax incentives. The main directions of the Concept: reduction of the tax burden on the payroll; improvement of taxation of payers of generally established and simplified taxes; implementation of measures aimed at reducing the negative impact of improving tax policy on payers of the simplified tax regime; improvement of the procedure for calculating and paying value added tax and excise tax.

Uzbekistan is implementing measures aimed at carrying out deep structural transformations and improving the economic mechanism. Among them, tax instruments play an important role, with the help of which the state has the opportunity to stimulate the development of industrial production. Foreign experience has been widely used in the development of tax mechanisms in the field of income tax, VAT, excise tax, property tax, as well as in improving tax administration tools in Uzbekistan. To this end, significant changes have been made to the tax system and a new Tax Code has been introduced that meets modern requirements.

The creation of new digital technologies and the improvement of artificial intelligence are the main engine of the fourth industrial revolution. The perfection of digital programs and the success of their implementation in the spheres of society become the core of a new economic model and form the ratings of states in the global world.

The development of the digital economy is a priority of global reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the goals of which are to increase the competitiveness of the national economy and improve the quality of life of citizens. A modern state is unthinkable without a tax system and its effective legal regulation. The digitalization process transforms the administration of mandatory payments – from For purely fiscal purposes, the tax authorities are moving towards targeting service companies. Digitalization of tax administration is aimed at transparency of business operations of private entities in order to determine the true tax liability [1].

Literature review. At the same time, both specialists who carry out their activities in the system of tax authorities and scientists do not have a common opinion on the definition of the term "tax administration". In particular, A.V.Ugryumova notes that this term is "applied haphazardly, there is no unified understanding of its content"[2].

Thus, A.M.Mamurov defines it as "...enhanced tax administration, regulated by regulatory acts in the field of taxation, which ensures the taxation of certain objects in a market economy ..." [3]. In turn, M.S.Mishenina and L.V.Maksimova understand tax administration as a set of procedures that ensure public administration in the field of taxation. Tax administration has a targeted focus on the implementation of tax legislation [4]. It is worth noting that O.A. Tolkachev defines tax administration as a tool for implementing tax policy and includes in the tax administration system, in particular, tools of tax (fiscal) control, including taxpayer control capabilities, "Taxpayer's Personal Account", VAT control systems, online cash registers and other systems created using IT-technologies [5]. E.G.Shurdumova and D.M.Kankulov understand tax administration as an organizational system that helps to implement the tax policy of the state [6]. Obviously, tax administration is considered here from the point of view of its organizational function, the work of tax authorities to ensure the receipt of tax revenues to the budget and tax control. According to L.I. Goncharenko, tax administration is only an integral element of such a broad concept as "management of the tax system". And the latter should be considered in a broad sense (as the activity of the state aimed at managing each element of the tax system) and in a narrow sense (as the management of tax authorities) [7].

From this it can be concluded that tax administration is based on normative legal acts (tax legislation), organizational activities of tax authorities for the implementation of tax policy and tax control. The approach presented by V.G.Knyazev and L.Ya. Marshavina is quite interesting, where tax administration is part of the management process that has certain special features, among which are "engineering of tax relations", procedural (institutional) mediation and the predominance of the control function [8]. At the same time, E.A.Fedorov, in collaboration with other researchers [9], defines the tax administration system as a complex that includes:

- planning and forecasting of the tax burden based on the accounting of taxpayers (individuals and legal entities);
- control, including a system of control measures (control of timely submission of declarations, tax audits, tax monitoring, control of transactions);

- analysis related to the study of the effectiveness of taxation and the work of tax authorities, contributing to the development of measures aimed at improving taxation and tax administration.

It becomes obvious that tax control in this definition is an element of tax administration, and tax administration is a set of measures.

In the scientific works of A.V.Grishchenko, who summarized the results on the essence and interpretation of the concept of "tax administration" given by other authors, it is substantiated that tax administration is a systemic activity of authorized (specialized) public authorities. In this context, the activity is aimed at the implementation and improvement of tax legislation, ensuring the effective functioning of the tax system and tax control[10]. In his opinion, tax administration is much broader than the concept of "tax control", it includes not only registration, accounting, control of taxpayers, objects of taxation, but also is associated with the analysis of the effectiveness of taxation, tax burden, and the development of changes in the tax system.

Analysis. The tax authorities use about two dozen software information systems. Digital technologies in the tax sphere are being rapidly improved and supplemented with new ones. However, taxpayers do not have the opportunity to study the algorithm of their work, since there is no legal regulation, and the documentation is stamped (for official use).

Technical failures and errors in system settings increase the separation of the practical activities of tax authorities from the requirements of the legislation on taxes and fees, which undermines taxpayers' trust in digital resources. At the same time, the possibility of taking into account such shortcomings is practically not found in the legislation on taxes and fees of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which leads to negative consequences, among which one can single out: an increase in state expenditures in connection with compensation to the taxpayer for his violated rights; a decrease in confidence in the processes of digitalization, leading to a decrease in motivation for their use; a decrease in the economic activity of business entities and capital outflow, etc.[3]

Issues of ensuring the security of the individual, society and the state in the application of information technologies, the circulation of digital data are of constitutional value and belong to the exclusive powers of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Taxation of digital products and online services is an equally important problem for the implementation of fiscal functions not only for the Republic of Uzbekistan, but also for all economically developed countries. Electronic sales

and transactions are difficult to control, since the identity of the buyer can now be established often only by bank card data, and if payment is made through an electronic payment system, it is almost impossible. The lack of reliable technology creates endless opportunities for tax evasion. Therefore, it is impossible to do without the development of new technologies that will allow tax authorities to identify and track transactions in cyberspace.

The creation of a single digital platform will allow tax authorities to improve their work with data arrays, increase the efficiency of interaction with taxpayers, and promote the acquisition and development of new competencies. With the introduction of digital technologies, the current procedure for registration of legal entities and individual entrepreneurs will lose relevance, since it will take place mainly in "real time" mode. Also, with the transition to predominantly "digital" addresses, determining the actual address of the location of legal entities will lose its meaning. individuals and individual entrepreneurs.

The interaction between the participants in the tax process will take place in a virtual network of fiscally transparent taxpayers. For the majority of disciplined taxpayers, the tax payment procedure will be simplified and implemented without their participation, which will enable tax authorities to strengthen control over potential violators. Digitalization in the tax system will make it possible to completely abandon filling out tax returns.[9]

Thus, digitalization in the economic system as a whole and in the taxation system, in particular, in modern economic conditions is not only an objective necessity, but also contains a number of undeniable advantages, including:[7]

- administration of tax relations with the help of modern technologies, including in the virtual space;
- creating conditions for transparency and accessibility for taxpayers;
- solving the problem of double taxation by using a single international standard for digital identification.

In conclusion, One of the priority tasks of the control unit in 2023 is the prompt suppression of tax evasion schemes and the reduction of the shadow economy. It is necessary to hold accountable both the beneficiaries and the organizers of the activities of the sites, the heads of one-day firms. In cases where the taxpayer does not wish to voluntarily abandon the use of the scheme, the main tool ensuring the principle of fairness and inevitability of punishment is an on-site tax audit.

In order to improve the administrative and legal mechanism for the introduction of digital technologies into the tax system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, coordinated work on digitalization should be carried out together with the business community of the country, taking into account the need for cyber protection of databases.

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